

The Influence of Information Searching Behavior, Perceived Benefits of Information Search, and Alternative Attractiveness on Switching Intentions of Marketplace Users in Indonesia and Individualism Level as a Moderator

Reza Fahlevi,
Mas Wahyu Wibowo
Faculty of Economics and Business
Mercu Buana University, Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- This research develops the behavior of consumers' switching intentions for marketplace applications using the PPM framework. The independent variables are: (1) information searching behavior; (2) perceived benefits of information searching; and (3) alternative attractiveness, while the dependent variable is switching intentions, with individualism level as the moderating variable. The target population in this research is consumers who have more than one marketplace application, with a sample size of 200 respondents. The analysis technique used is SEM-PLS, with the following research results: (1) Information searching behavior has a positive and significant effect on switching intention; (2) perceived benefits of information search have no positive and significant effect on switching intention; (3) alternative attractiveness has a positive and significant effect on switching intention; (4) individualism level does not moderate the relationship between information searching behavior and the consumer's switching intention; (5) the individualism level does not moderate the relationship between the benefits of information search and the consumer's switching intention; (6) individualism level moderates the relationship between the alternative attractiveness and the consumer's switching intention.

Keywords:- Push-pull-mooring, Switching intention, Marketplace, Indonesia.

I. INTRODUCTION

Online marketplaces are places where products can be bought and sold. The marketplace sector is developing quickly in the contemporary global period, which has made rivalry among marketplace businesses more intense. In order to satisfy the market's (consumers') increasingly diversified demands and wants, this forces businesses to compete for product innovations. Given that technology and humans are increasingly inseparable, particularly in terms of the requirement for online shopping and selling, and given that

the pandemic has recently limited people's ability to engage in activities outside the home, people are becoming more passionate about this sector.

Indonesian people have high enthusiasm for using the marketplace. This is a result of Indonesia's growing internet and smartphone populations. In addition, the marketplace industry is very practical to use and very helpful in buying and selling goods online. So it's no wonder that many Indonesian people are enthusiastic about adopting this technology.

According to the study organization We Are Social in April 2021, it released a list of ten countries with the world's fastest-growing marketplaces. Indonesia leads the ranks of these countries with 88.1% growth. The fact that Indonesia has more than 100 million internet users is one of the reasons supporting the market's development. The second position is UK, with 86.9% of internet users using the marketplace. Then there are 86.2% of internet users in the Philippines who use the marketplace (katadata, 2021).

According to the Top Brand Award (2020), there are currently three marketplace brands that have the highest percentage of Top Brands in Indonesia. Lazada has been ranked at the top for three consecutive years, but there has been a significant decrease in 2021 from the previous year's 31.9% to 15.2%, and in the same year Shopee experienced a significant increase from 20% in the previous year to 41.8%. Based on these data, one might conclude that there is a consumer migration between Indonesian marketplaces. These three brands continue to innovate to create excellence by fulfilling consumer needs and wants in order to win their hearts.

There is so many marketplace in Indonesia gives consumers the opportunity to easily switch brands from one brand to another. According to Karmila (2017), businesses with a low level of brand loyalty will lose less than 20% of their consumers in 5 years, however businesses with a high level of brand loyalty will lose half of their customers in that

time. In order to prevent customers from switching to other brands, businesses must be able to keep and pay attention to customer loyalty even while they already have it (Haridasan et al., 2021).

The level of consumer loyalty is negatively correlated with the different conveniences the market has to offer. 42% of users still have low levels of loyalty, according to the Sensus Survey research on market trends for 2022. The behavior of users, who have continued to often move between services over the past three months, is evidence of this, according to a study performed online with 1,000 respondents in five major cities in Indonesia.

According to Haridasan et al. (2021), the majority of today's consumers are multi-channel consumers, or consumers that use many channels or services in their shopping process. This practice of switching brands is described in their study. The decision to switch brands is a complicated one that can be influenced by multiple of factors. A Push-Pull-Mooring model was developed by Bansal et al. (2005) to explain the phenomenon of consumer migration.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW, CONCEPTUAL MODEL, AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

➤ *Push-Pull-Mooring (PPM Model):*

One theory that discusses the phenomenon of customer switching is the Push-Pull-Mooring Theory (PPM). The PPM theory was developed by Bansal et al. (2005) and is commonly used as a research model by previous researchers to examine human migration in geography. However, theoretically, this theory also applies to other scientific behaviors. In the concept of human migration, a person migrates from one place to another, then in the context of customer switching, customers switching from one service provider to another (Bansal et al., 2005).

PPM theory is a concept that is often used in research on migration (switching). This concept suggests that there are negative factors early in a process that encourage consumers to switch service brands. Meanwhile, the positive factors contained in the intended action will attract or direct the prospect of migrants to their destination. The push and pull factors will then interact with the inhibiting factors, which will be a process in restraining potential migration (switching) or even facilitating migration to a new place; it can be interpreted that these inhibiting factors have a moderating effect on the relationship between the push factor and switching intentions and the relationship between the pull factor and switching intentions. This theoretical concept has been used successfully in the marketing literature to predict consumer migration or change in behavior (Haridasan et al., 2021).

➤ *Switching Intention:*

According to Haridasan et al. (2021), switching intention is defined as customer incentive to discontinue use of an existing service and switch to another service. Desire to switch is described as a signal to either partially or

entirely detach the customer from the previous service provider (Jabeen et al., 2015). Switching still allows consumers to keep associations with previous providers while adopting new behaviors to some extent. While switching totally means that users have abandoned the previous service in favor of a new one.

➤ *Push Effects:*

According to Bansal et al. (2005), push effect is a factor consisting of various variables that can encourage consumers to switch service brands from the one they are currently using to another service brand. There are two variables included in the category of driving factors, which will be described below.

A. *Information Searching Behavior:*

Information searching behavior is the consumer effort involved in gathering product- or purchase-related information from external sources. Previous research on information seeking has classified information seeking sources as internal and external factors. Internal search refers to information available in consumers' memories, while external search refers to searching for external sources of information, such as advertisements, product packaging, and other formal sources of information (Chang et al., 2017). Purchase information searching behavior for product information from different sources (multichannel) has received significant attention in the marketing literature (Chang et al., 2017). Therefore, knowledge of consumer search behavior can help marketers develop more effective strategies to influence consumer switching decisions.

Based on the premise above, we believe that consumers who refer to most sources of information are multi-channel consumers who show a behavioral tendency to switch service brands. This statement is supported by Haridasan et al. (2021) and Chang et al. (2017), which state that information searching behavior has a positive and significant influence on consumers' switching intentions. Therefore, we posit that:

✓ *H1: Information searching behavior have a positive and significant effect on the switching intention.*

B. *Perceived Benefits of Information Search:*

Perceived benefits of information search stem from the economic paradigm of information search. The benefits of searching for information across multiple channels are that it can reduce the uncertainty of purchasing decisions, help find the best prices, and obtain information more efficiently (Chang et al., 2017). Search benefits and costs are important determinants of consumer information searching activity because search benefits are results that can increase one's utility or provide values. Perceived information search benefits are thus defined as the perceived benefits consumers expect resulting from searches related to the product they want to buy. As a result, the advantages of searching for information across multiple channels are considered to help someone switch service brands.

Based on the premise above, we believe that the perceived benefits of information search in various multi-channels will encourage consumers to switch service brands. This statement is supported by Chang et al. (2017), who revealed that the perceived benefits of information search has a positive and significant effect on consumer switching intentions. Therefore, we posit that:

✓ *H2: Perceived benefits of information search have a positive and significant effect on the switching intention.*

➤ *Pull Effect:*

Pull factors are positive factors that direct prospective migrants to their goals and are characteristics in other places that are relatively distant but appealing.

• *Alternative Attractiveness:*

Alternative attractiveness is one of the key variables that influences a person to switch to another channel. Alternative attractiveness is defined as the consumer's perception of the possibility of consumer satisfaction among competing alternatives in the market (Chang et al., 2017). Therefore, alternative attractiveness means that the expected results of other alternatives can be better than the previous service brand, which will motivate consumers to switch. Thus, this study concludes that the more alternatives available or the higher the perceived value of the alternatives consumers have, the less likely it is they will maintain a relationship with the previous service brand, which facilitates switching behavior.

Based on the premise above, we believe that the perceived benefits of information search in various multi-channels will encourage consumers to switch service brands. This statement is supported by (Haridasan et al., 2021; Chang et al., 2017; Bansal et al., 2005), who revealed that alternative attractiveness has a positive and significant effect on consumer switching intentions. Therefore, we posit that:

✓ *H3: Alternative attractiveness have a positive and significant effect on the switching intention.*

➤ *Mooring Effect:*

Mooring factors are aspect that will facilitate or impede consumers from switching from one service to another. Mooring factor, as described by Bansal et al. (2005), has a moderating effect on the relationship between push factors and switching intentions as well as the relationship between pull factors and switching intentions.

• *Individualism Level:*

Individualism, according to Yanto (2020), is a social pattern in which individuals have loose links and consider themselves as an autonomous group with no influence from others. Individualism may also be defined as a cultural ideal in which people isolate themselves from society and concentrate on themselves (Wardani, 2020). In the context of the switching intention, consumer individualism has a wants to switch on the basis of wants or self-motivation without any influence from others.

Based on the premise above, we believe that those three independent variables—information searching behavior, perceived benefits of information search, and alternative attractiveness have a moderating effect on consumer switching intentions. Therefore, we posit that:

✓ *H4: The influence of information searching behavior on switching intentions will be stronger if the level of individualism is high.*

✓ *H5: The influence of perceived benefits of information search on switching intentions will be stronger if the level of individualism is high.*

✓ *H6: The influence of alternative attractiveness on switching intentions will be stronger if the level of individualism is high.*

➤ Figure 1 Shows the Conceptual Framework of this Study.

Fig 1 Conceptual framework

III. METHOD

➤ *Population and Sampel:*

The population in this study is made up of consumers who have more than one marketplace application on their phone. The researchers used the non-probability sampling methodology and the purposive sampling method in this study. Purposive sampling, according to Sugiyono (2015), is a sample technique with specific concerns. Researchers utilize purposeful sampling since the population number is

uncertain. The samples in this study were users who met particular requirements, namely those who had more than one marketplace application on their phone.

According Hair et al. (2017), recommends to using GPower 3.1 software to calculate the number of sample. The sample size is determined with a 5% parameter error, a 95% statistical power, and a number of predictors of 4. The G-Power calculation is illustrated below:

Fig 2 GPower Size Sampling

Based on the figure above, the total sample size obtained is 129 people. The number of questionnaires distributed will be 200 in order to acquire stronger statistical power.

➤ *Sample Characteristics:*

The majority of respondents (58.5%) were female. The majority (43.5%) of respondents are between the ages of 18 to 25. Furthermore, 54% of respondents had a bachelor's degree or higher. However, the majority of respondents (62%), work full - time employed. Furthermore, the majority of respondents earn between 3.000.000 to 5.000.000 IDR per month.

➤ *Technique and Data Analysis:*

This study used the Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) statistical analysis technique. The data analysis technique in this study used the PLS technique, which was carried out in 2 stages, the first of which was to test the measurement model, namely the construct validity and reliability of each indicator. The second stage is to test the structural model, which aims to determine whether there is an influence between the variables or correlation between the constructs as measured using the t test of the PLS.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS OF RESEARCH

❖ *Measurement Model:*

A. *Convergent Validity:*

The convergent validity test is shown by the loading factor value for each construct, where the recommended loading factor value is 0.7 or higher for confirmatory research and between 0.6 or 0.7 for exploratory but acceptable research, and the average variance extracted (AVE) value must be higher than 0.5. (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 1 Convergent Validity Test Result

Variable	Indicator	Factor Loading	Cut-off Value	AVE	Ket
Information Searching Behavior	ISB1	0,874	0,70	0,755	Valid
	ISB2	0,881	0,70		Valid
	ISB3	0,842	0,70		Valid
	ISB4	0,873	0,70		Valid
	ISB5	0,929	0,70		Valid
	ISB6	0,870	0,70		Valid
	ISB7	0,808	0,70		Valid
Perceived Benefits of Information Search	PBIS1	0,860	0,70	0,697	Valid
	PBIS2	0,859	0,70		Valid
	PBIS3	0,844	0,70		Valid
	PBIS4	0,836	0,70		Valid
	PBIS5	0,773	0,70		Valid
Alternative Attractiveness	AA1	0,684	0,70	0,687	Valid
	AA2	0,843	0,70		Valid
	AA3	0,898	0,70		Valid
	AA4	0,791	0,70		Valid
	AA5	0,907	0,70		Valid
Individualism Level	IL1	0,792	0,70	0,635	Valid
	IL2	0,840	0,70		Valid
	IL3	0,796	0,70		Valid
	IL4	0,848	0,70		Valid
	IL5	0,734	0,70		Valid
	IL6	0,765	0,70		Valid
	IL7	0,797	0,70		Valid
Switching Intention	SWI1	0,885	0,70	0,736	Valid
	SWI2	0,905	0,70		Valid
	SWI3	0,799	0,70		Valid
	SWI4	0,886	0,70		Valid
	SWI5	0,837	0,70		Valid
	SWI6	0,829	0,70		Valid

Based on Table 1, it can be concluded that each indicator value of the loading factor and AVE value above the suggested value, specifically 0.70 for the loading factor and 0.50 for the AVE value (Hair et al., 2017).

B. *Discriminant Validity:*

The AVE square root for each construct being higher than the correlation between constructs in the Fornell & Larcker model, and the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio being less than 0.9, indicate good discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2017). Discriminant validity testing resulted in the following results:

Table 2 Discriminant Validity Test

Fornell & Larcker Model					
	AA	IL	PBIS	ISB	SWI
AA	0,829				
IL	0,496	0,797			
ISB	0,620	0,498	0,835		
PBIS	0,665	0,528	0,805	0,869	
SWI	0,709	0,576	0,671	0,752	
Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio					
	AA	IL	PBIS	ISB	SWI
AA					
IL	0,550				
ISB	0,683	0,547			
PBIS	0,718	0,563	0,872		
SWI	0,767	0,620	0,731	0,798	

Based on table 2, it shows that the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct is higher than the correlation between one construct and the other constructs in the model. Then the constructs in the estimated model fulfill the criteria of discriminant validity. Based on table 2, it shows that the value of HTMT in each construct is less than 0.9. So the constructs in the estimated model fulfill the criteria of discriminant validity.

C. Construct Reliability:

The Cronbach's alpha value and the composite reliability value of each construct show the construct reliability test. In confirmatory research, the composite reliability value must be higher than 0.7. Whereas for exploratory research, composite reliability and Cronbach alpha value of 0.6 to 0.7 are still acceptable (Hair et al., 2017). The results of construct reliability testing are as follows:

Table 3 Construct Reliability Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
DTA	0,884	0,916
IL	0,904	0,924
MPI	0,891	0,920
PPI	0,946	0,956
SWI	0,928	0,943

Based on table 3, each indicator has a cronbach's alpha and composite reliability value that is higher than the suggested value, which is in the range of 0.6 to 0.7 for Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values. This confirms that all of the constructs or variables in this study have been considered reliable.

➤ *Collinearity:*

Table 4 Collinearity Test

Influence	Score VIF
PPI > SWI	3,548
MPI > SWI	3,078
DTA > SWI	1,993

VIF (variance inflation factor) is the square root of the increased standard error rate, where the higher standard error rate is produced by collinearity. Table 4 shows that the VIF value of each indication is less than 5.

➤ *Fit Test:*

Table 5 Fit Test

Parameter	Score
SRMR	0,063
NFI	0,949
RMSttheta	0,085

According to table 4, the SRMR value is 0.063, showing that the model fulfills the goodness of fit model's criteria and has a perfect fit. Meanwhile, the NFI value is more than 0.9, which is 0.949, showing that the model is acceptable.

❖ *Structural Model:*

Table 6 Structural Model (R^2, Q^2, f^2)

Influence	R^2	Q^2	f^2	Effect Size
SWI	0,709	0,503		
PPI > SWI			0,131	Small to medium
MPI > SWI			0,006	Small
DTA > SWI			0,159	Medium to large

A. *Coefficient of Determination R-Square:*

Based on table 5, it shows that the model of the influence of independent variables (information searching behavior, perceived benefits of information search, and alternative attractiveness) on switching intention have R-Square (R^2) of 0,709, or 70,9%, which can be interpreted as meaning that 70,9% of switching intention can be explained by information searching behavior, perceived benefits of information search, and alternative attractiveness, while 29.1% can be influenced by other factors.

B. *Predictive Relevance Q-Square:*

Based on table 5, the variable model has a Q-Square (Q^2) value of 0.503, showing that the variable model in this study has predictive relevance because the Q-Square (Q^2) is higher than 0.

C. *Coefficient of Determination F-Square:*

Based on table 5, the F-Square (f^2) value for the influence of information searching behavior on the switching intention is 0.131, indicating a small to medium effect size. Meanwhile, the influence between the benefits of information search on switching intention is 0.006, indicating a small effect size, while influence the alternative attractiveness on switching intention is 0.159, indicating a medium to large effect size.

➤ *Hypothesis Test:*

Based on the findings of hypothesis testing, it is conclude that:

- T-statistic value for the H1 hypothesis test in this study was 5.095, the P value was 0.000, and the original sample value was 0.368. The T-statistic is higher than the T-table value of 1.65, the P value is less than the suggested value of 0.05, and the original sample value is positive. These findings show that information searching behavior has a positive and significant effect on switching intention, which has supported.
- T-statistic value for the H2 hypothesis test in this study was 1,078, the P value was 0,140, and the original sample value was 0,075. The T-statistic is less than the T-table value of 1.65, the P value is higher than the suggested value of 0.05, and the original sample value is positive. These findings show that perceived benefits of

information search has not positive and significant effect on switching intention, which not supported.

- T-statistic value for the H3 hypothesis test in this study was 5,413, the P value was 0.000, and the original sample value was 0,304. The T-statistic is higher than the T-table value of 1.65, the P value is less than the suggested value of 0.05, and the original sample value is positive. These findings show that alternative attractiveness has a positive and significant effect on switching intention, which has supported.
- T-statistic value for the H4 hypothesis test in this study was 0,655, the P value was 0,256. The T-statistic is less than the T-table value of 1.65, the P value is higher than the suggested value of 0.05, and the original sample value is positive. These findings show that individualism level does not moderate the relationship between information searching behavior on switching intention.
- T-statistic value for the H5 hypothesis test in this study was 1,514, the P value was 0,065. The T-statistic is less than the T-table value of 1.65, the P value is higher than the suggested value of 0.05, and the original sample value is positive. These findings show that individualism level does not moderate the relationship between perceived benefits of information search on switching intention.
- T-statistic value for the H6 hypothesis test in this study was 1,757, the P value was 0,039. The T-statistic is higher than the T-table value of 1.65, the P value is less than the suggested value of 0.05, and the original sample value is positive. These findings show that individualism level does not moderate the relationship between alternative attractiveness on switching intention.

Table 7 Hypothesis Test

Influence	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Ket
ISB> SWI	0,368	0,072	5,095	0,000	Supported
PBIS > SWI	0,075	0,069	1,078	0,140	Not Supported
AA > SWI	0,304	0,056	5,413	0,000	Supported
ISB*IL*SWI	0,043	0,066	0,655	0,256	Not Supported
PBIS*IL*SWI	-0,137	0,090	1,514	0,065	Not Supported
AA*IL*SWI	0,109	0,062	1,757	0,039	Supported

V. CONCLUSION

Information searching behavior has a positive and significant effect on switching intention. The findings of this hypothesis test support previous research by Chang et al. (2017), which found a positive and significant relationship between information searching behavior on switching intention. This is because multi-channel shoppers (those who switch across marketplace applications) consumer frequently using their mobile phones to compare products, pricing, and reviews from other customers and these are some of the factors that contribute to a stronger potential for consumers to switch.

Perceived benefits of information search has not positive and significant effect on switching intention. The results of this hypothesis test are supported several previous research, such those published by Matondang et al. (2019) and Afandi (2020), show that the push factor has a weak relationship to switching intention. According to Bansal et al. (2005), push factors are variables that motivate consumers to switch previous applications that are assumed to have a negative impact. This means that in this study, the variable indicators of the perceived benefits of information search, such as getting more information, getting the best prices, and getting promotional information, are not the main factors for consumers to switch marketplace service applications, but rather other factors, such as pull factors, which are connected to the marketplace service applications.

Alternative attractiveness has a positive and significant effect on switching intention. The results of this hypothesis test are supported several previous research, such those published by Bansal et al. (2005), Jung et al. (2017) and Haridasan et al. (2021). This is caused by the fact that consumers who participate in multi-channel shopping (consumers who prefer to switch marketplace applications) prefer to switch because they believe other applications have a more beneficial offer than the previous application.

Individualism level has not been proven to influence the relationship between information searching behavior on switching intention. The results of this hypothesis test are supported several previous research, such those published by Bansal et al. (2005), Jung et al. (2017), and Haridasan et al. (2021) prove that the moderating variable or mooring factor does not moderate the relationship between the push factor and customer switching intention.

Individualism level has not been proven to influence the relationship between perceived benefits of information searching on switching intention. The results of this hypothesis test are supported several previous research, such those published by Bansal et al. (2005), Jung et al. (2017), and Haridasan et al. (2021) prove that the moderating variable or mooring factor does not moderate the relationship between the push factor and customer switching intention.

Individualism level has been proven to influence the relationship between alternative attractiveness on switching intention. The results of this hypothesis test are supported several previous research, such those published by Bansal et al. (2005), Jung et al. (2017), and Haridasan et al. (2021) prove that the moderating variable or mooring factor moderate the relationship between the pull factor and customer switching intention.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Afandi, M. A. (2020). Switching Intentions Among Millennial Banking Customers to Fintech Lending. *International Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance (IJIEF)*.
- [2]. Al-Mashraie, M., Chung, S. H., & Jeon, H. W. (2020). Customer switching behavior analysis in the telecommunication industry via push-pull-mooring framework: A machine learning approach. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*.
- [3]. Astuti, Y. (2019). Perilaku Switching Behavior Pengguna Electronic Commerce (e-Ceommerce) di Kota Langsa dengan Model Migrasi Konsumen Push, Pull Mooring.
- [4]. Award, T. B. (2020). Data Presentase Pengguna Mobile Banking di Berbagai Bank di Indonesia Tahun 2018-2019.
- [5]. Bansal, H. S. (2005). "Migrating" to New Service Providers: Toward a Unifying Framework of Consumers' Switching Behaviors. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*.
- [6]. Chang, H. H., Wong, K. H., & Li, S. Y. (2017). Applying push-pull-mooring to investigate channel switching behaviors: M-shopping self-efficacy and switching costs as moderators. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*.
- [7]. Chin, W. W., Peterson, R. A., & Brown, S. P. (2008). Structural equation modeling in marketing: Some practical reminders. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*.
- [8]. Dean, D., Suhartanto, D., & Kusdibyo, L. (2019). Predicting Destination Image in Creative Tourism: A Comparative between Tourists and Residents. *International Journal of Applied Business Research*.
- [9]. Djusmin, V., & Dirgahayu, R. T. (2019). Push Pull Mooring dan Pyschological Ownership terhadap Perilaku Beralih Pengguna Instant Messaging. *Indonesian Journal of Information Systems*.
- [10]. Guo, J., Shan, S., Wang, Y., & Khan, Y. A. (2021). Analyzing Chinese Customers' Switching Intention of Smartphone Brands: Integrating the Push-Pull-Mooring Framework. *Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society*.
- [11]. Haridasan, A. C., Fernando, A. G., & Balakrishnan, S. (2021). Investigation of consumers' cross-channel switching intentions: A push-pull-mooring approach. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*.

- [12]. Hsieh, J.-K., Hsieh, Y.-C., Chiu, H.-C., & Feng, Y.-C. (2012). Post-adoption switching behavior for online service substitutes: A perspective of the push-pull-mooring framework. *Computers in Human Behavior*.
- [13]. Jabeen, S., Hamid, A. B. A., & Rehman, S. U. (2015). Switching Intentions: A Case of Saudi Arabian Hypermarkets. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*.
- [14]. Jung, J., Han, H., & Oh, M. (2017). Travelers' switching behavior in the airline industry from the perspective of the push-pull-mooring framework. *Tourism Management*.
- [15]. Kim, S., Choi, M. J., & Choi, J. S. (2019). Empirical Study on the Factors Affecting Individuals' Switching Intention to Augmented/Virtual Reality Content Services Based on Push-Pull-Mooring Theory.
- [16]. Li, C.-Y., & Ku, Y.-C. (2018). The power of a thumbs-up: Will e-commerce switch to social commerce? *Information & Management*.
- [17]. Matondang, T. P., Prastawa, H., & Mahachandra, M. (2019). Pengaruh Faktor Push, Pull, dan Mooring Terhadap Keinginan Berpindah Pelanggan. *Industrial Engineering Online Journal*.
- [18]. Schiffman dan Kanuk. 2008. Perilaku konsumen. Edisi 7. Jakarta: Indeks.
- [19]. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods For Business: A Skill Building Approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [20]. Sugandha, A. P., & Indarwati, T. A. (2021). Pengaruh Push, Pull, dan Mooring terhadap Switching Intention pada Konsumen Pengguna Wifi di Era Pandemi Covid-19. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*.
- [21]. Sugiyono. (2011). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R&D*. Alfabeta.
- [22]. Sugiyono. (2015). *Metode Penelitian dan Pengembangan*. Alfabeta. Bandung.
- [23]. Susanty, A., Handoko, A., & Puspitasari, N. B. (2020). Push-pull-mooring framework for e-commerce adoption in small and medium enterprises. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*.
- [24]. Yang, L.-Q., Spector, P. E., Sanchez, J. I., Allen, T. D., Poelmans, S., Cooper, C. L., Lapierre, L. M., O'Driscoll, M. P., Abarca, N., Alexandrova, M., Antoniou, A.-S., Beham, B., Brough, P., Çarıkçı, I., Ferreira, P., Fraile, G., Geurts, S., Kinnunen, U., Lu, C., ... Woo, J.-M. (2012). Individualism-collectivism as a moderator of the work demands-strains relationship: A cross-level and cross-national examination. *Journal of International Business Studies*.
- [25]. Yanto, J. (2021). Pengaruh Orientasi Kewirausahaan terhadap Kinerja UMKM di Jabodetabek dengan Individualisme sebagai Variabel Moderasi. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis dan Kewirausahaan*.
- [26]. Zeng, Z., Li, S., Lian, J.-W., Li, J., Chen, T., & Li, Y. (2021). Switching behavior in the adoption of a land information system in China: A perspective of the push-pull-mooring framework.